

eccenca

mastering complexity

EUROCLEAR

Leipzig ASCM - APICS

Business Digital Twin **BOSCH**

NAVAL EDM **Daimler** **BERLIN**

Council Innovate with Data

>50% Growth **NOKIA**

Volkswagen 60 FTE

Knowledge Graph

DBPedia **SIEMENS**

DaaS/Cloud

TOTAL

Hyderabad

90%

DB PERFORMANCE

Graph VISUALISATION

Machine Learning

AGILE Feature-Focused APPROACH DRIVES ISOLATED SOLUTIONS

ACHIEVE SUBSTAINABILITY ??

QUAGMIRE

NEW KPIs

RE-USE +

RE-PURPOSING

OF KNOWLEDGE

across projects

**A NEW CHALLENGE IN TOWN THAT
CALLS FOR A NEW APPROACH**

**HYPER
AUTOMATION**

**WE PREDICT:
Massive adoption of**

**HYPER
AUTOMATION**

2030

50%

What is HYPERAUTOMATION

Hyperautomation maturity levels

ACHIEVE
SUSTAINABILITY

RE-USE RE-PURPOSE

MEET AND EXCEED YOUR
INTERNAL CUSTOMER
EXPECTATIONS!

Product Centric automation journey of our customers

AND here is the BUSINESS CASE

[...that should make your mouths water!]

FUNDAMENTALLY CHANGING THE RUNCOST FROM ESCALATING TO CONTINUOUSLY DECREASING

- RUN
- TRANSFORM
- GROW

WORLD LEADING REUSE COMPANY

10x

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IS THE WORLD LEADING DATA ACTIVATION AND RE-USE PLATFORM

DATA USE

ACCOUNTING

SALES

ENGINEERING

MANUFACTURING

QUALITY

OUTBOUND AND CONSUMPTION

RE-BUNDLE, RE-PURPOSE, RE-USE

UN-BUNDLE AND ENRICH

INBOUND DATA SOURCES

File

Database

Property Graph

Datawarehouse

API

RDF Graph

SEEING IS BELIEVING

10x

CURRY COMPANY

Powered by eccenca corporate memory

Tickle your success buds with Corporate Memory

Inventory challenge

Process monitoring

Re-use

85.71%

$$\text{Re-use} = \frac{\text{Total vocabularies} - \text{New internal vocabularies}}{\text{Total vocabularies}}$$

- Re-used vocabularies from other projects**
 Internal vocabularies : 1
 External vocabularies : 4
- New vocabularies**
 Internal vocabularies : 1
 External vocabularies : 1

Re-purpose

98.46%

$$\text{Re-purpose} = \frac{\text{Total classes} - \text{New classes added}}{\text{Total classes}}$$

- Re-purposed classes from other projects : 2050**
- New classes : 32**

CURRY COMPANY

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Tickle your success buds with Corporate Memory

www.eccenca.com

Scan the QR code below to know more about the
curry company

Or visit us at

<https://bit.ly/cchyper>

Or

<https://eccenca.com/resources/curry-company-hyperautomation>

Curry Company

Inventory Challenge

Discover all the recipes based on your Ingredient selection

STEP-1

Select the ingredients from an assortment of the given categories.

STEP-2

Feed in your preferences based on the cuisine you want

STEP-3

Pick and choose any recipe from your personalised recipe catalogue.

STEP-4

Customise your recipe by choosing alternative ingredients for the given!

Start Cooking!

Process Challenge

Discover all the recipes based on your Ingredient selection

STEP-1

Select the ingredients from an assortment of the given categories.

STEP-2

Feed in your preferences based on the cuisine you want.

STEP-3

Pick and choose any recipe from your personalised recipe catalogue.

STEP-4

Alter your cooking conditions and check what the outcome is going to be.

Start Cooking!

Reuse/Repurpose

Curry Company

Use Case #1: Product Configurator with “smart substitution capabilities”

Home

Inventory Challenge

Process Challenge

Home

HiHbrockm | Logout [→]

Inventory Challenge
Discover all the recipes based on your Ingredient selection.

Select the ingredients → Enter your preferences → Select a recipe from the catalogue → Substitute the ingredients or serve as is!

Recipe catalogue > Chettinad style chicken roast recipe

Ingredient Details

- Number of Ingredients
50
- Ingredient Quantity
 - 1 sprig curry leaves
 - salt - to taste
 - 1 onion - sliced
 - 1 teaspoon ghee
 - 1/2 teaspoon turmeric powder (haldi)
 - 1/4 teaspoon methi seeds (fenugreek seeds)
 - 1 teaspoon fennel seeds (saunf)
 - 4 cloves garlic
 - 1 teaspoon sunflower oil
 - 1 teaspoon whole black peppercorns

Substitute an ingredient

Servings
3

Under The Hood

Ingredient Details

Time Statistics

Recipe Instructions

Reuse/Repurpose

Feedback/Support

Curry Company

Use Case #1: Product Configurator with “smart substitution capabilities”

The screenshot displays the Curry Company web application interface. The browser address bar shows the URL <https://curry-company.eccenca.com>. The page features a navigation sidebar on the left with options: Home, Inventory Challenge (selected), and Process Challenge. The main content area is titled "Inventory Challenge" and includes a sub-header "Discover all the recipes based on your Ingredient selection." Below this is a four-step process flow: 1. Select the ingredients (checked), 2. Enter your preferences (checked), 3. Select a recipe from the catalogue (checked), and 4. Substitute the ingredients or serve as is! (with a warning icon). The current recipe selected is "Chettinad style chicken roast recipe" from the "Recipe catalogue". A "Reuse/Repurpose" button is visible in the sidebar. The main content area is divided into three sections: "Ingredient List" with a "Reset" and "Save Changes" button, "Substitute Generator" showing a list of substitutes for "1 teaspoon sunflower oil", and a "Time Statistics" section. The "Ingredient List" includes items like "1 sprig curry leaves", "salt - to taste", "1 onion - sliced", "1 teaspoon ghee", "1/2 teaspoon turmeric powder (haldi)", "1/4 teaspoon methi seeds (fenugreek seeds)", "1/2 teaspoon fenugreek seeds (haldi)", "1 teaspoon fennel seeds (saunf)", "4 cloves garlic", "1 teaspoon sunflower oil" (highlighted in orange), "1 teaspoon sunflower peanut oil", "1 teaspoon whole black peppercorns", and "1/2 teaspoon mustard seeds". The "Substitute Generator" lists substitutes for "1 teaspoon sunflower oil": "1 teaspoon sunflower olive oil", "1 teaspoon sunflower peanut oil", "1 teaspoon sunflower sesame oil", "1 teaspoon sunflower coconut oil", "1 teaspoon sunflower gingelly oil", and "1 teaspoon sunflower sunflower oil".

Home

Inventory Challenge

Process Challenge

Reuse/Repurpose

Feedback/Support

Inventory Challenge

Discover all the recipes based on your Ingredient selection.

Select the ingredients

Enter your preferences

Select a recipe from the catalogue

Substitute the ingredients or serve as is!

Recipe catalogue > Chettinad style chicken roast recipe

Under The Hood

Ingredient List

Reset Save Changes

Substitute Generator

List of substitutes for :

1 teaspoon sunflower oil

1 teaspoon sunflower olive oil

1 teaspoon sunflower peanut oil

1 teaspoon sunflower sesame oil

1 teaspoon sunflower coconut oil

1 teaspoon sunflower gingelly oil

1 teaspoon sunflower sunflower oil

1 sprig curry leaves

salt - to taste

1 onion - sliced

1 teaspoon ghee

1/2 teaspoon turmeric powder (haldi)

1/4 teaspoon methi seeds (fenugreek seeds) -----> 1/2 teaspoon fenugreek seeds (haldi)

1 teaspoon fennel seeds (saunf)

4 cloves garlic

1 teaspoon sunflower oil -----> 1 teaspoon sunflower peanut oil

1 teaspoon whole black peppercorns

1/2 teaspoon mustard seeds

Curry Company

Use Case #1: Product Configurator with “smart substitution capabilities”

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL <https://curry-company.eccenca.com>. The page header includes the Eccenca logo and navigation links for 'Hilbrockm' and 'Logout'. The main content area is titled 'Under The Hood > Smart Substitution' with the subtitle 'Capturing and digitising curry knowledge'. A 'Back To Recipe Information' link is visible in the top right.

The interface features a central recipe graph for 'Chettinad style chicken roast recipe'. The graph is a radial network with the recipe name at the center, connected to various ingredients and their quantities. The ingredients shown include: Onion (1), Card (1/2 cup), Dry red chillies (2), Tamarind (1 tablespoon), Black pepper (1 teaspoon), Fennel seeds (1 teaspoon), Cloves (2), Curry leaves (1), Chicken (1), Oil (1 tablespoon), Cardamom (1), Ghee (1), Mustard seeds (1/2 teaspoon), Cinnamon (1/2 inch), Coriander (2 tablespoons), Jaggery (1 teaspoon), Kalonji (1/4 teaspoon), Ghee (1 tablespoon), and Milk fat (Class). Some ingredients are further linked to properties like 'Greasy texture' and 'Nutty flavor'.

On the left side, there is a vertical navigation menu with four icons: 'Raw Data', 'Vocabulary Graph', 'Recipe Graph', and 'Smart Substitution' (which is highlighted).

On the right side, there is a panel titled 'Ingredient' showing 'Ghee: 1 tablespoon'. Below it, a section 'Substitutes available:' lists several options: Salted butter, Parmesan cheese (with checkboxes for Flavour, Texture, and Class), Mozzarella cheese, Fetta cheese, Cottage cheese, Classic mayonnaise, Cheese, Cheese spread, Cheese slices, and Cheese mix.

Curry Company

Use Case #1: Product Configurator with “smart substitution capabilities”

Smart substitution

Reuse

Statistics

Smart substitution

Total vocabularies used : 5

Internal : 1

External : 4

Classes used : 2050

Curry Company

Use Case #2: Automating process monitoring with IoT

The screenshot displays the 'Process Challenge' section of the Curry Company web application. The interface includes a navigation sidebar on the left with 'Home', 'Inventory Challenge', and 'Process Challenge' (the active page). The top right corner shows the user 'Hhbrockm' and a 'Logout' link. A progress bar at the top indicates the current step: 'Process monitoring'.

The main content area is titled 'Process Challenge' and includes the instruction: 'Discover all the recipes based on your Ingredient selection.' Below this is a recipe catalogue entry for 'Chettinad style chicken roast recipe'. A vertical sidebar on the left of the recipe details offers options: 'Process', 'Time Statistics', and 'Ingredient Details'. A 'Reuse/Repurpose' button is located at the bottom of this sidebar.

The recipe details are organized into three process steps, each with a description and IoT monitoring controls:

- Sautéing:** Heat oil in a heavy bottomed pan, on medium flame. Add onions, coconut, ginger and garlic and saute till the onions become soft and the coconut turn light brown in colour. IoT time (mins): 10, IoT temperature (°C): 100.
- Roasting:** Heat a heavy bottomed pan. Add chettinad spice mix ingredients - includes cumin seeds, coriander seeds, fenugreek seeds, kalonji, black peppercorn, dry red chillies, fennel seeds, cinnamon stick, cloves, cardamom and mustard seeds. Dry roast them for about 2 Dry roast. IoT time (mins): 7, IoT temperature (°C): 80.
- Boiling:** Now, add these spices into a mixer grinder and grind it into a powder. Heat ghee in the same pan and add this Chettinad spice mix into the ghee. After 30 seconds, add the chicken along with all the marinade. Mix everything well, add the tamarind pulp, jaggery and 1/4 cup of water. Cover the pan and boil till the chicken is 3/4th done. IoT time (mins): 5, IoT temperature (°C): 80.

Each IoT control includes a 'Reset' button and an 'Apply' button. To the right of the process steps is a 'Process rating' section, which includes a description of the rating system and two interactive areas: 'Recipe flavour' and 'Recipe texture'. A 'Final outcome' section is also present.

At the bottom left, there is a 'Feedback/Support' button.

Curry Company

Use Case #2: Automating process monitoring with IoT

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mastering complexity

Under The Hood > Vocabulary Graph
Capturing and digitising curry knowledge

Process Data
Vocabulary Graph
Process Graph
Process Monitoring

Process monitoring

Reuse

Process monitoring

Total vocabularies used : 7

Internal : 2

External : 5

Classes used : 2082

Curry Company

Inventory challenge

Process monitoring

Re-use 85.71%

Re-purpose 98.46%

NEW MEASUREMENT RESUSE & REPURPOSE

100 x

SUMMARY

Industry must change focus

Hyperautomation requires new approach

New paradigm: Re-use / Re-purpose

Proof is in the pudding: Curry Company

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